

Revisiting Governance in Family Enterprises: Can Independent Directors and Generational Leadership Shape Financial Performance?

First and Corresponding Author: Dr Puneeta Goel, Professor, Amity College of Commerce and Finance, Amity University, Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Second Author- Dr Kanu Priya, Research Scholar, Amity College of Commerce and Finance, Amity University, Noida, India.

Abstract

Purpose: While family boards may provide valuable insights and maintain a long-term focus, independent directors offer external perspectives and strategic oversight for improving business performance. This study examines the extent of family ownership and the role of independent directors in moderating the relationship between family presence on the board and the financial performance of Indian listed family-owned business (FOB). Furthermore, this study also examines how family leadership across different generations influences financial performance.

Design: Using a random-effects meta-regression model, we analyse data from 2010 to 2024 for 337 publicly listed Indian companies, of which 184 were identified as FOB according to the study's criteria, and 153 were non-family-owned businesses.

Findings: The results highlight that family ownership of around 50% is the optimal threshold for maximising financial performance; beyond this level, financial performance begins to decline. Board independence emerges as a critical moderating factor in the relationship between family board control and the financial performance of non-governmental organisations. Second-generation family involvement consistently shows a positive and significant relationship with all financial performance indicators.

Originality: The study analyses the multi-dimensional impact of family involvement, including ownership, board participation, and leadership, on the financial performance of family-run businesses, which account for 85% of Indian firms.

Practical Implications: The study offers practical guidance on optimal family governance and leadership structures to help FOBs thrive in a complex, competitive market. This generational analysis gives a comprehensive understanding of how leadership transitions could influence family business performance and strategies.

Keywords: Family-owned business; Family Board control; Independent Director; Generational Leadership; Financial Performance.

JEL: G30; L25; M10

1. Introduction

Family-owned businesses (FOBs) represent the most enduring and prevalent form of corporate ownership worldwide and are the key contributors to national economies (Bodolica et al., 2020). Their distinct emphasis on long-term orientation, prudent financial management, and strong relational capital enables them to sustain competitive advantage across generations. In India, FOBs range from small entrepreneurial ventures to large, diversified conglomerates, many of which are publicly listed. As these firms transition from privately held to publicly traded entities, they face the dual challenge of maintaining family control while meeting market expectations for transparency, accountability, and performance (Keasey et al., 2015).

India presents a particularly compelling context for examining family enterprises, given the pervasive dominance of family ownership and control. Approximately 73% of the top 500 companies listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) are family-owned, and nearly half of Nifty-listed firms are managed by second or third-generation family members (The Economic Times, 2013). Deloitte further estimates that family-run businesses account for 85% of all Indian firms, making a substantial contribution to national output and employment. The concentration of family ownership gives rise to governance and decision-making structures that differ markedly from those of non-family firms, thereby shaping strategic priorities and performance outcomes in distinct ways (Goel et al., 2012).

The prominence and success of Indian family businesses reflect broader global patterns. Evidence from the University of St. Gallen and Ernst & Young underscores the economic significance of family-owned enterprises worldwide. According to the EY Family Business Index 2023, the top global family businesses generated \$8.02 trillion in revenue, a remarkable 10% increase since 2021. Indian FOBs share key attributes that have driven their global success, including careful resource management, a long-term strategic horizon, and a strong focus on financial resilience. These characteristics enable family firms to maintain strong balance sheets, allowing them to withstand market fluctuations and economic uncertainties (Neubaum et al., 2017). Additionally, preserving cultural values and intergenerational goodwill strengthens stakeholder trust and fosters community relationships, contributing to sustained success (Jaskiewicz et al., 2015; EY, 2021).

While family boards provide valuable insights and maintain a long-term focus, family members' involvement can introduce biases or groupthink that may hinder effective decision-making. In this context, the independent directors play a critical role in the governance of FOBs. As non-family, non-executive members, independent directors offer objective oversight, ensure that the board's decisions are in the best interests of all stakeholders, and mitigate the adverse effects of family control on firm performance. They help balance the controlling family's dynastic aspirations with the strategic needs of

the business, thereby improving governance quality and accountability (Sarbah et al., 2015). However, despite the growing regulatory and academic emphasis on board independence, limited attention has been paid to how independent directors moderate the relationship between family involvement and firm performance.

Another defining feature of family enterprise is generational succession. As family businesses transition across generations, the role and influence of each generation on business practices and decisions evolve (Bauweraerts et al., 2023). First-generation entrepreneurs typically emphasise financial performance, growth, and survival, whereas subsequent generations often shift focus towards intellectual capital, brand reputation, innovation, and human resource development (Gene & Gallizo, 2021). The simultaneous involvement of multiple generations within a family business introduces a complex dynamic that can either enhance or constrain firm performance (Muttakin et al., 2014). Examining performance variations across generational stages, therefore, provides a deeper understanding of how intergenerational leadership shapes the financial performance of family firms.

Prior studies examining the relationship between family involvement and firm performance have yielded mixed and sometimes contradictory findings (Evert et al., 2018; Rouyer, 2016). While some studies highlight that family ownership enhances stewardship, commitment, and strategic stability, others point to potential drawbacks such as nepotism, limited professionalism, and entrenchment (Sacristan-Navarro et al., 2011; Poutziouris et al., 2015). These inconsistencies in the literature are often attributable to differing definitions, methodologies, and contextual factors across studies. To address this, the present study adopts a context-specific definition of a family-owned business: one in which the founder's family holds at least 20% of the outstanding shares and at least two family members serve on the board of directors (Wu et al., 2021; Ramachandran et al., 2018).

Building on this foundation, the study investigates the multi-dimensional impact of family involvement, through ownership, board participation, and leadership, on financial performance. It further examines the moderating role of board independence and the differential effect of generational involvement on firm outcomes. Drawing on agency theory, stewardship theory, the resource-based view (RBV), and intergenerational theory, the research provides a comprehensive framework for the governance-performance nexus in Indian family enterprises.

Empirically, the study employs a longitudinal panel dataset of NSE 500 firms over fifteen years (2010–2024) sourced from the CMIE Prowess database. By examining financial performance, this research contributes to the growing literature on corporate governance and performance in family firms, particularly in emerging economies.

Overall, the study contributes to theory and practice by demonstrating that while family control can enhance financial outcomes through stewardship and aligned incentives, its benefits may diminish

beyond a threshold, necessitating professional oversight and stronger governance mechanisms. The findings offer important implications for policymakers, investors, and family business leaders seeking to design governance structures that balance family legacy with sustainable competitiveness.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Family Ownership and Financial Performance

Family ownership is widely recognised as a defining characteristic of corporate governance, particularly in emerging economies where concentrated ownership structures prevail (Villalonga & Amit, 2006). From the perspective of Agency Theory, family ownership aligns the interests of owners and managers, because family members often occupy both ownership and managerial roles (Jensen & Meckling, 1983). This convergence reduces principal-agent conflicts, limits information asymmetry, and curbs opportunistic behaviour, thereby fostering a long-term strategic orientation and enhancing firm value (Koji et al., 2020; Muttakin et al., 2014).

However, when ownership becomes excessively concentrated, the benefits of family firms may become limited. The risk of principal-principal conflict increases and may lead to entrenchment, tunnelling, and nepotism, where family members prioritise private benefits over shareholder value (Morck & Yeung, 2003). Consequently, several empirical studies have consistently found a non-linear (inverted U-shaped) relationship between family ownership and firm performance, reflecting that performance improves up to an optimal ownership threshold but declines thereafter (Poutziouris et al., 2015; Srivastava & Bhatia, 2022).

This non-linear relationship is salient in the Indian context, where family promoters often maintain controlling stakes even in the publicly listed firms. While moderate family ownership may facilitate efficient decision-making and stewardship, excessive concentration could constrain innovation and professional management (Gupta & Nashier, 2017; Gill & Kaur, 2015). These governance trade-offs underscore the need to identify ownership thresholds that distinguish value-enhancing and value-destroying family control. Thus, this study aims to explore the optimal threshold level of family ownership that maximises the financial performance.

2.2 Family Board Representation and Financial Performance

Family representation on the board of directors is a critical governance mechanism that shapes decision-making and firm outcomes. Boards with a substantial presence of family members may promote unity of vision, faster decision-making, and preserving firm-specific knowledge. However, such concentration may limit board diversity, weaken independent oversight, and limit exposure to external perspectives, thereby affecting responsible governance and accountability (Anderson & Reeb, 2003).

From the perspective of Stewardship Theory, family members serving on boards tend to act as stewards of the firm's legacy and reputation, prioritising collective welfare and firm longevity over short-term personal gains (Neubaum et al., 2017). Their intrinsic motivation, loyalty, and sense of identity with the firm often lead to superior monitoring and long-term strategic orientation (Miller & Le Breton-Miller, 2017).

Empirical evidence, however, highlights a nuanced relationship. While a family-dominated board can enhance financial stability and relational capital, excessive representation may hinder professional governance and constrain strategic debate (Bhatt & Bhattacharya, 2017; Reddy & Wellalage, 2023). These competing effects suggest a need to examine the role of family board representation in enhancing firm performance.

2.3 Moderating Role of Board Independence

An emerging body of research highlights the role of independent directors as a crucial counterbalance to concentrated family control (Sani, 2020). From the Agency Theory perspective, independent directors provide objective oversight, protect minority shareholders, and enhance transparency in decision-making. Their presence mitigates potential conflicts arising from self-interested family decisions and reduces the likelihood of entrenchment and expropriation, particularly in firms with dominant family influence (Pandey et al., 2011).

Complementing this, the Resource-Based View (RBV) posits that independent directors contribute valuable human and social capital to the firm, including expertise, networks, and experience, thereby enhancing governance and strategic outcomes (Sarbah et al., 2015). In family firms, such resources can support the professionalisation of management, facilitate access to specialised knowledge, and foster innovation, without diluting the core family ethos and long-term orientation (Thorning-Lund, 2012; Bazhair & Sulimany, 2023).

Empirical findings suggest that board independence enhances performance, particularly when balanced with family representation rather than substituting it entirely (Koji et al., 2020). Independent directors can strengthen the positive stewardship effects of family involvement while curbing the risks of excessive family control. Accordingly, this study posits that board independence positively moderates the relationship between family board representation and financial performance.

2.4 Intergenerational Involvement and Financial Performance

The Intergenerational Theory emphasises that the sustainability of family firms depends on effective transfer of knowledge, leadership, and values across generations (Lambrecht & Lievens, 2008). Founding generations typically exhibit entrepreneurial drive, commitment, and deep organisational knowledge, leading to strong performance outcomes during early stages of a firm's lifecycle

(Muttakin et al., 2014). The close alignment between ownership and control in family-led firms strengthens strategic coherence and decision-making.

However, as firms transition to second- or later-generation leadership, governance and performance dynamics tend to evolve. Dilution of founder control leads to intra-family conflict, weakens strategic focus and adversely affects performance (Yu & Cai, 2017; Moreno-Gené & Gallizo, 2021).

Evidence from emerging economies suggests that family-led firms often outperform professionally managed firms when founder-CEOs retain control, but this tends to diminish across generations (Chahal & Sharma, 2022; Muttakin et al., 2014). Empirical studies reveal mixed results. While founder-led firms often outperform later-generation firms due to concentrated authority and entrepreneurial vision, second- or third-generation leaders can excel when they integrate modern governance practices and innovation (Sunon et al., 2022). Understanding these intergenerational effects is therefore critical for explaining heterogeneity in performance outcomes among family-owned firms.

The extant literature provides valuable insight into the relationship between family involvement and firm performance. However, the mixed and contradictory findings leave gaps in the research due to variations in ownership thresholds, governance mechanisms, and institutional contexts. Secondly, the moderating role of independent directors in shaping the governance-performance relationship remains limited in the literature for family-owned businesses in developing economies. Moreover, empirical evidence on how generational leadership influences financial performance across different stages of succession, especially in emerging markets, remains fragmented. The present study addresses these gaps by examining the multidimensional impact of family involvement, the presence of independent directors and intergenerational succession on firm performance. This study seeks to provide a more comprehensive and context-specific understanding of the governance-performance nexus in family enterprises.

2.5 Research Framework

Figure 1 represents the proposed research framework which examines the influence of family involvement in business on firm performance. Family involvement is represented by family members' share ownership and their presence on the board. The study analyses the moderating role of independent directors in enhancing the firm performance of family-owned businesses. Further, the framework incorporates family generational involvement in shaping financial outcomes. By integrating these dimensions within a single empirical model, the framework enables a comprehensive examination of how family control can both create and constrain value in publicly listed Indian family firms.

Figure 1: Research Framework

3. Method

3.1 Research Design and Approach

This study employs a quantitative, explanatory research design to investigate the impact of family involvement on firm performance among Indian listed family-owned businesses (FOBs). A panel data approach was employed, combining cross-sectional and time-series data to capture both firm-specific and temporal variations. This design provides more robust estimation by controlling for unobserved heterogeneity across firms and improving the accuracy of causal inferences. The analysis covers 15 years (2010–2024), enabling the study to account for dynamic changes in governance structures, leadership succession, and market conditions.

3.2 Sample Selection

The study draws on a sample of firms listed on the National Stock Exchange (NSE) 500 Index which represents approximately 95% of India's total market capitalisation. The Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE) ProwessIQ database served as the primary data source, providing audited financial and governance information. To ensure data reliability and comparability, the sample was restricted to publicly listed, non-financial, and non-utility firms with continuous data for at least 10 years during the study period (2010–2024) and ownership and board composition disclosures. After applying these selection criteria and excluding missing observations, the final balanced panel comprised 337 firms,

of which 184 were identified as FOB according to the study's criteria and 153 were non-family-owned businesses.

3.3 Identification of Family-Owned Firms

Consistent with prior research (Villalonga & Amit, 2006; Zhang et al., 2025; Bang et al., 2018), a firm was classified as *family-owned* if the founding family or their descendants collectively held at least 20% of the firm's equity and at least two family members served on the board of directors or in a top management position. This dual criterion ensures that the classification captures both ownership control and active family involvement in governance. Firms that did not meet these criteria were categorised as non-family firms.

3.4 Variable Measurement

Table I: List of Variables under Study

Variable Type	Variable Name	Abbreviation	Measurement / Definition
Dependent Variables	Financial Performance	ROA	Return on Assets
		ROE	Return on Equity
		ROCE	Return on Capital Employed
		ROS	Return on Sales
Independent Variables	Family Ownership	FOWN	Percentage of total shares held by the founding family
	Family Board Representation	FBR	Proportion of family members on the board to total board size
	Generational Involvement	GEN	Categorical variable: 1 = Founder-led (First Generation), 0 = Successor-led (Second or Later Generation)
Moderating Variable	Board Independence	BIND	Proportion of independent directors on the board
Control Variables	Foreign Ownership	FOROWN	Percentage of shares owned by foreign individual and institutional investors.
	Domestic Institutional Ownership	DIOWN	Percentage of shares owned by domestic institutional investors.
	Firm Size	SIZE	Natural logarithm of total assets
	Leverage	LEV	Total debt divided by total assets

	Firm Age	AGE	Number of years since incorporation
	Growth	GROWTH	Annual percentage change in sales

Source: Created by the Author

In this study, we winsorized the financial performance indicators by substituting the lowest and highest 1% of the observations with the values at the 1st and 99th percentiles, respectively. Winsorization helps mitigate the adverse effects of outliers while retaining the insight that these observations represent extreme values within the distribution. Before performing panel data regression analysis, it is crucial to conduct a unit root test to verify the stationarity of the data. The results indicate that for all these variables, the bias-adjusted t-statistics are significant at the 5% significance level. Therefore, all the mentioned variables are stationary in the panel data.

Model Specification

Panel regression models were estimated to test the proposed hypotheses. The baseline model for firm performance is expressed as follows:

$$FP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FOWN_{it} + \beta_2 FOWN^2_{it} + \beta_3 FBR_{it} + \beta_4 BIND_{it} + \beta_5 (FBR \times BIND)_{it} + \beta_6 GEN_{it} + \sum \beta_k Controls_{it} + \mu_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where:

- FP_{it} = financial performance for firm i in year t
- μ_i = unobserved firm-specific effect
- λ_t = time effect
- ε_{it} = error term

Before running the panel data regression, several diagnostic tests are conducted. The test for heteroscedasticity across all regression models shows a significant chi-square at the 5% significance level, indicating unequal error variances and the presence of heteroscedasticity. Autocorrelation testing is performed using the Wooldridge test for serial correlation. The findings indicate that the F-statistics for all models are significant at the 5% significance level and that there is first-order autocorrelation in all models. Consequently, the problem of autocorrelation exists in most of the models. To ensure multicollinearity is not present in the data, VIF scores should be below 10, and tolerance values should be above 0.10. The results show that the highest VIF score is 2.74 and the lowest tolerance value is 0.36 for FBR, indicating that multicollinearity is not a significant issue in the data used for this study. Additionally, the mean VIF is 1.51.

To analyse the impact of family involvement on the financial performance of the companies, dynamic panel data regression has been used. The study has employed Two-Step SGMM to overcome the problems of heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation and endogeneity.

4. Result Analysis

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
ROA	9.87	6.95	-9.33	32.32
ROE	15.73	12.02	-18.07	51.07
ROCE	24.37	23.36	-25.66	74.59
ROS	10.68	11.19	-17.04	54.56
FOWN	26.67	26.33	0.00	75.00
FBR	0.26	0.24	0.00	0.69
FOROWN	13.09	24.26	0.00	80.43
DIOWN	24.51	13.60	0.00	79.37
BIND	0.44	0.15	0.10	0.88
GROWTH	1.40	10.24	0.00	356.06
LEV	1.45	2.54	0.00	69.75
SIZE	3.41	0.64	0.23	5.99
AGE	39.60	24.70	1.00	159.00

Source: Calculated by Author using STATA 15

From a researcher's perspective, the descriptive statistics highlight considerable heterogeneity among Indian listed firms in terms of ownership concentration, governance composition, and performance outcomes. The average family ownership of 26.7%, ranging between 20-75%. The mean family board ratio was 0.36, indicating that more than one-third of board members were family affiliates, and 44% independent board representation suggests a balanced yet diverse governance structure, reflecting varying degrees of family influence, institutional participation, and strategic orientation across firms.

The VIF and tolerance values indicate no significant multicollinearity in the study's data, with the highest VIF at 2.74, the lowest tolerance at 0.36, and a mean VIF of 1.51, all well within acceptable thresholds supporting the robustness of the regression models.

4.2 Regression Analysis: Family Ownership and Financial Performance

To examine the effect of family ownership on firm financial performance, a dynamic panel data regression analysis using a Two-step System Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) is employed, with clustering at the firm level.

Table 4.2: Impact of FOWN on Financial Performance

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables											
	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3			Model 4		
	ROA			ROE			ROCE			ROS		
	Coeff.		t-value	Coeff.		t-value	Coeff.		t-value	Coeff.		t-value
Lagged DV	0.562	*	11.09	0.512	*	10.41	0.624	*	13.27	0.492	*	5.16
FOWN	0.013	*	2.38	0.024	*	2.26	0.045	*	2.92	0.022	*	1.97
FOROWN	0.017	*	2.72	0.041	*	3.57	0.039	*	2.42	0.01		1.05
DIOWN	0.036	*	3.44	0.063	*	3.4	0.091	*	3.46	0.07	*	3.05
BIND	0.097		0.18	-1.212		-1.18	-0.099		-0.05	-0.192		-0.22
GROWTH	-0.031	*	-5.66	0.001		0.04	0.024		1.02	-0.011		-0.58
LEV	-0.191	*	-3.39	-0.264	*	-2.43	-0.425		-1.66	-0.391	*	-3.42
SIZE	-1.07	*	-3.56	-2.421	*	-5.19	-1.914	*	-3.05	-0.169		-0.37
log AGE	0.13		0.51	0.305		0.65	0.674		1.14	0.263		0.63
Constant	6.279	*	4.14	12.879	*	5.59	9.87	*	3.38	3.212		1.7
Chi-sq	786.046, p = 0.00			392.955, p = 0.00			390.11, p = 0.00			205.462, p = 0.00		

* $p < 0.05$; Source: Calculated by Author using STATA 15

Table 4.2 shows that the coefficient of the lagged dependent variable is positive and statistically significant for all models ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that past performance (e.g., ROA, ROE, ROCE, and ROS) is a significant predictor of current performance, indicating that firms that performed well in the past are likely to continue to perform well. The coefficient for FAMOWN is positive and statistically significant across all models ($p < 0.05$), indicating that higher family ownership is associated with better financial performance (ROA, ROE, ROCE and ROS). This suggests that family ownership may be a positive factor influencing financial outcomes, possibly due to long-term orientation, stewardship, or greater alignment of interests between owners and the firm. Further, the results indicate that control variables, particularly foreign ownership (FOROWN), domestic ownership (DIOWN), and leverage, have a significant impact on financial performance, with some differences across financial performance metrics. Board independence (BIND) and firm age do not significantly influence performance in this sample.

To test whether family-owned businesses (FOBs) exhibit the same behaviour when accounting for nonlinearities, we modify our regression by including both the percentage of family ownership and its squared term. The results are presented in Table III. The findings suggest that the relationship between family ownership and performance is nonlinear (inverted U-shaped), indicating that family influence initially confers a positive premium but eventually becomes negative.

Table 4.3: Determining the Optimum Family Ownership Level

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables											
	Model 5			Model 6			Model 7			Model 8		
	ROA			ROE			ROCE			ROS		
	Coeff.	*	t-value	Coeff.	*	t-value	Coeff.	*	t-value	Coeff.	*	t-value
FOWN	0.280	*	5.69	0.415	*	5.31	0.027		0.69	0.340	*	4.58
FOWNsq	-0.331	*	-3.53	-0.419	*	-2.84	0.531		1.81	-0.310	*	-2.42
FOROWN	0.036	*	9.25	0.071	*	10.73	0.079	*	4.99	0.018	*	5.1
DIOWN	0.076	*	11.26	0.111	*	7.91	0.164	*	5.2	0.134	*	11.54
BIND	-0.993		-1.32	-4.706	*	-3.07	-4.426		-1.61	0.021		0.02
GROWTH	-0.073	*	-7.47	-0.061	*	-3.12	0.036		1.05	-0.038	*	-3.08
LEV	-0.596	*	-7.2	-0.556	*	-5.08	-2.244	*	-7.88	-1.117	*	-7.84
SIZE	-1.731	*	-6.84	-2.956	*	-5.82	-2.658	*	-3.19	0.088		0.22
log AGE	0.560	*	2.93	0.708	*	1.97	1.736	*	4.82	0.370	*	1.97
Constant	12.275	*	10.1	21.468	*	9.33	24.727	*	9.8	6.128	*	4.74
Chi-sq	981.18, p = 0.00			633.14, p = 0.00			206.21, p = 0.00			725.29, p = 0.00		
Adj. R sq	0.113			0.0683			0.0838			0.1042		
Inflection Point	42.29%			49.52%			No Inflection point			54.83%		

* p < 0.05; Source: Calculated by Author using STATA 15

Table 4.3 shows that, when financial performance is measured by ROA, ROE, and ROS, the regression coefficient for FAMOWN is positive, whereas that for FAMOWNsq is negative. This suggests an inverted U-shaped relationship between FAMOWN and these financial performance measures, indicating that performance initially increases and then decreases as the family's stake in the firm rises. More specifically, the inflexion points at which the positive effect of FAMOWN begins to taper off are approximately 42.29% for ROA and 49.52% for ROE, but no inflexion point is found for ROCE. The inflexion point for the quadratic relationship is given by $(-)\beta_1/2\beta_2$. We conclude that increasing family ownership concentration may lead to additional risks and non-stewardship attitudes among family members. Overall, the analysis indicates that family ownership and firms' financial performance do not exhibit a uniform linear relationship across the entire range of family shareholding. Financial performance decreases with increasing family ownership up to a certain level, as indicated by the inflexion points between 42% and 50%. Beyond this level, financial performance begins to decline as family ownership increases further.

4.3 Family Board Representation and Moderating Effects of Board Independence

To investigate the impact of family presence on the board of directors (BOD) on the financial performance, the study employs the two-step system GMM estimator of the dynamic panel model, which accounts for unobservable heterogeneity, autocorrelation, and endogeneity issues by utilising instrumental variables. To address endogeneity, the first lag of these variables is used as an instrument.

Table 4.4: Impact of Family on Board and Moderating Impact of Independent Directors

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables											
	Model 9			Model 10			Model 11			Model 12		
	ROA			ROE			ROCE			ROS		
	Coeff.		t-value	Coeff.		t-value	Coeff.		t-value	Coeff.		t-value
FBR	0.245		0.2	-1.184		-0.52	-3.346		-0.77	2.059		1.05
BIND	-2.802	*	-3.97	-6.741	*	-4.85	-11.18	*	-4.21	-3.216	*	-2.83
FBR*BIND	5.244	*	2.49	8.944	*	2.15	23.46	*	2.95	5.202		1.54
FOROWN	0.031	*	2.88	0.057	*	3.13	0.065		1.92	0.028		1.63
DLOWN	0.065	*	4.49	0.111	*	4.29	0.18	*	3.67	0.09	*	3.84
GROWTH	-0.06	*	-4.22	-0.034		-1.3	0.019		0.37	-0.036		-1.59
LEV	-0.288	*	-9.39	-0.393	*	-6.5	-1.214	*	-10.52	-0.591	*	-11.99
SIZE	-2.055	*	-7.4	-4.548	*	-9.08	-2.816	*	-2.97	1.05	*	2.35
log AGE	1.896	*	5.7	2.026	*	3.51	2.475	*	2.28	0.7		1.31
Constant	9.343	*	8.62	23.574	*	11.85	24.929	*	6.61	3.288		1.88
Chi-sq	222.354, p = 0.00			220.745, p = 0.00			160.639, p = 0.00			202.322, p = 0.00		
Adj. R sq	0.115			0.08			0.139			0.127		
Moderating Effect	Yes			Yes			Yes			No		

* p < 0.05; Source: Calculated by Author using STATA 15

Table 4.4 presents the results of regression models (Model 4-6), which examine the impact of FBR on financial performance indicators (ROA, ROE, ROCE and ROS). The Family Board Ratio (FBR) has a positive and significant impact on financial performance, i.e. on ROA and ROS. It suggests that having more family members on the board of directors is associated with better financial outcomes for the firm. This could be due to long-term commitment, strategic stability, or better alignment of ownership and management. Family members on board can better leverage their assets to generate profits (ROA) and are more efficient at utilising capital to generate returns (ROCE).

To test the moderating effect of board independence (BIND) on the relationship between Family Board (FBR) and financial performance indicators, namely ROA, ROE and ROCE, we incorporate the interaction term (FBR×BIND) between the primary explanatory variable (FBR) and the moderator variable (BIND). The interaction between FBR and BIND yields positive and significant results across all measures of financial performance. This evidence suggests that board independence positively moderates the relationship between the family board and firms' financial performance. The positive moderating result indicates that the superior monitoring provided by independent directors may prompt family managers to develop policies that enhance performance.

4.4 Intergenerational Involvement and Performance

To examine intergenerational management differences that arise during the succession of family businesses and their impact on profitability, we compared the performance of companies led by first-generation family businesses with that of second- and subsequent-generation family businesses, focusing on specific characteristics to better understand how generational transitions influence family business performance.

Table 4.5: Impact of Generation Involvement on Financial Performance

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables											
	Model 13			Model 14			Model 15			Model 16		
	ROA			ROE			ROCE			ROS		
	Coeff.		t-value	Coeff.		t-value	Coeff.		t-value	Coeff.		t-value
FirstGEN	0.076		0.22	1.007		1.61	-1.228		-1.02	1.806	*	3.17
SecondGEN	0.934	*	3.74	1.993	*	4.51	2.848	*	3.34	0.891	*	2.21
LaterGEN	-0.668		-1.58	-0.611		-0.81	-1.213		-0.84	-0.7		-1.02
FOROWN	0.026	*	6.07	0.055	*	7.37	0.035	*	2.44	0.001		0.14
DIOWN	0.066	*	8.93	0.096	*	7.29	0.144	*	5.68	0.117	*	9.8
BIND	-0.933		-1.47	-4.683	*	-4.17	-3.833		-1.77	0.132		0.13
GROWTH	-0.077	*	-8.45	-0.067	*	-4.16	0.018		0.59	-0.044	*	-3.00
LEV	-0.597	*	-16.19	-0.559	*	-8.56	-2.261	*	-17.94	-1.126	*	-18.86
SIZE	-1.701	*	-10.43	-2.861	*	-9.91	-2.724	*	-4.89	0.173		0.66
log AGE	0.438	*	2.87	0.495		1.83	1.286	*	2.47	0.175		0.71
Constant	13.412	*	20.02	23.183	*	19.53	29.706	*	12.98	7.93	*	7.32
F-value	61.14, p = 0.00			34.53, p = 0.00			42.76, p = 0.00			55.23, p = 0.00		
Adj. R sq.	0.1063			0.0622			0.0763			0.0987		

* p < 0.05; Source: Calculated by Author using STATA 15

Table 4.5 indicates that family businesses run by the second generation tend to have a positive and significant association with ROA, ROE, ROCE and ROS compared to those managed by first-generation or later generations. SecondGEN bring fresh ideas, professional management practices, strategic foresight, and the ability to innovate, all of which can help the family business adapt to new challenges and seize new opportunities. Lower profitability in later generations has been commonly observed in the literature, often attributed to reduced relationship quality among family-member business administrators, exacerbated by higher levels of conflict. This finding reflects the greater willingness of subsequent generations to entrust the company to professionals outside the family. However, it may also stem from the difficulty in finding qualified replacements within the family.

5. Discussion

Family ownership in a business grants significant control, allowing families to influence firm performance. The objective of this study is to explore the relationship between family ownership and firm performance, with a specific focus on determining whether it is quadratic or non-linear. The results from the multivariate regression analysis confirm that financial performance is significantly and positively associated with family ownership. This outcome aligns with the findings of Anderson & Reeb (2003), Villalonga & Amit (2006), Miller et al. (2007), and Pandey et al. (2011), who observed similar patterns across different family business contexts. Family ownership (FAMOWN) shows a positive correlation with all the financial performance (FP) indicators (Ha et al., 2022; Minh Ha et al., 2022; Srivastava & Bhatia, 2022). This can be attributed to the extensive experience and operational sensitivity of family members developed over time in the business. By leveraging their long-term orientation, commitment, stability, and access to resources, the family-owned business can enhance their competitiveness and achieve sustainable financial success (Le Breton-Miller and Miller, 2009; Wu et al., 2025)

Additionally, the empirical analysis confirms a non-linear (inverted U-shaped) relationship between family ownership and financial performance, as measured by ROA and ROE but not with ROCE. However, family ownership squared shows a negative relationship with financial performance once it exceeds a threshold identified at 42%-55% ownership. This suggests that family-owned businesses (FOBs) should avoid high levels of family ownership beyond this inflexion point (Srivastava & Bhatia, 2022). The non-linear relationship between FAMOWN and firm performance is supported by previous studies by Pandey et al. (2011), Block et al. (2020), and Poutziouris et al. (2015). However, these results contrast with other empirical studies, such as Ha et al. (2022) and Shyu and Shen (2011), which suggest a U-shaped relationship between family ownership and firm performance. The findings suggest that firm performance improves initially as family ownership increases, due to the alignment effect. However, beyond a certain level of family ownership, performance begins to decline due to the entrenchment effect (Pandey et al., 2011; Anderson & Reeb, 2003).

The overall results of this study indicate that family involvement in top management is associated with superior firm performance. Specifically, the family board ratio is positively and significantly related to financial performance indicators such as ROA and ROCE. However, the relationship between the family board ratio and ROE is positive but not statistically significant. This suggests that having owners as managers in a family-owned business helps reduce agency costs arising from conflicts of interest between owners and managers, thereby enhancing business performance. Additionally, the positive impact of family board representation on financial performance may stem from the stewardship attitudes of family managers, who act in the company's best interests, given that the business is often the family's

primary asset. Giovanni (2010) and Villalonga & Amit (2006) have depicted both positive and negative relationships between family board presence and firm financial performance.

Moreover, the empirical analysis confirms a significantly positive moderating effect of independent directors on the relationship between family board representation and financial performance. The interaction term between FBR and BIND (FBR*BIND) serves as a moderating variable and has a significant, positive impact on ROA, ROE, and ROCE. These results are consistent with those of Sani (2020), Aguinis et al. (2017), and Jaggi et al. (2009). The study contributes to the resource-based view by confirming that firms with a substantial number of independent directors on the board are more likely to neutralise the entrenchment behaviour that may arise when there is a high proportion of family managers on the board.

The results on intergenerational impact on financial performance show that SecondGEN has a positive and significant effect on ROA, RONW, ROCE, ROS, and ROIC. The study contributes to the theory of entrepreneurs, which holds that the second generation tends to have a higher level of education, richer theoretical knowledge, and more energy than the founder or first generation. The first generation typically possesses a strong work ethic, extensive social networks, and wide-ranging experience (Yu & Cai, 2017). The results are consistent with Block et al. (2020), Kosmidou (2020) Sunon et al. (2022) and contribute to the intergenerational theory as the superior performance of second-generation family firms suggests effective transfer of firm-specific knowledge and strategic renewal, as successors blend founder values with professional management practices. However, the mixed performance of later-generation firms reflects increasing family complexity, diluted ownership, succession challenges, and potential erosion of shared vision. Intergenerational Theory posits that without formalised governance and succession planning; the advantages of family involvement diminish over time. The findings, therefore, highlight generational stage as a critical contingency in explaining performance heterogeneity among family firms.

6. Implications and Conclusion

The research findings indicate that family ownership positively affects financial performance when maintained at moderate levels (e.g., 42–54%). This aligns with the principle that agency costs are minimised when families exercise control without over-concentrating power. Aligning family ownership and management reduces conflicts of interest and fosters commitment to long-term goals. However, excessive concentration of family ownership can lead to entrenched interests, inefficiency, and potential mismanagement, ultimately harming firm performance. The findings also highlight the critical role of governance mechanisms in family businesses. By adopting robust governance practices, family businesses can protect minority shareholders' interests and ensure that management decisions benefit all stakeholders. From an agency perspective, increased family ownership mitigates the classic owner–

manager conflict by aligning ownership and control, thereby reducing monitoring costs and managerial opportunism. This alignment enhances operational efficiency and financial outcomes, particularly in family-controlled firms. From a stewardship perspective, family owners are motivated by long-term value creation, legacy preservation, and socio-emotional wealth, which encourage responsible governance and sustained firm performance. The convergence of agency cost reduction and stewardship-driven commitment explains the consistent positive relationship observed across both the present study and prior research.

The research findings suggest that family ownership and family representation on the board positively influence financial performance, aligning with the principles of stewardship theory. Family members act as stewards of the business, prioritising its long-term success over personal gains. The study further reveals that family-owned businesses perform better when there is a harmonious, cooperative relationship between family members and professional board members. Such collaboration fosters strategic alignment and enhances overall business success. This superior performance can be attributed to their focus on sustainable practices and relationship-building, which are essential for long-term resilience and growth. Additionally, the integration of the next generation into management ensures the sustainability of critical intangible assets, family knowledge, reputation, and networks, strengthening long-term competitive advantage. The findings align with intergenerational theory, which emphasises the importance of managing generational transitions to maintain continuity, preserve family legacy, and foster innovation. Family businesses that navigate these transitions successfully—through preparation, alignment of values, and strategic planning—are better positioned to sustain strong performance over time.

Excessive family control can lead to conservatism, authoritarianism, and conflicts with minority shareholders, thereby prioritising non-monetary gains over profitable ventures. Regulators and advisors should encourage family-owned businesses to avoid excessive concentration of power that may result in entrenchment, nepotism, or oligarchic behaviour. Policymakers should therefore encourage a balanced ownership structure in which non-family block holders can retain sufficient influence to ensure healthy governance practices. Appointments and promotions in family businesses should be based on merit and expertise, not family ties. Since subsequent generations may lack the entrepreneurial drive of their predecessors, families should actively work to nurture and sustain this entrepreneurial zeal across generations. A board with a significant number of independent directors is also recommended to enhance accountability and performance.

In today's rapidly evolving digital landscape, family-owned businesses must prioritise digital transformation as part of their innovation strategy. Moreover, the study provides important lessons for new business ventures. Family-owned businesses, through their intergenerational growth, have established successful models that other business families can emulate. New family firms can learn to

adapt to their enterprises' evolving needs while maintaining professionalism in their operations. This approach can help them achieve longevity and sustainability across generations.

The study primarily focuses on large, listed Indian firms, limiting the generalizability of the findings. Including small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) could provide a more comprehensive understanding of family-owned businesses. Incorporating non-financial measures such as credit ratings, brand value, customer satisfaction, and employee development could offer a more holistic view of how family involvement influences overall business performance. To enhance the generalizability of the results, future research could adopt a comparative approach by incorporating samples from multiple countries, allowing for cross-cultural and cross-regional analyses.

This research provides a comprehensive analysis of how family ownership, management, succession, and governance influence the financial and intellectual capital performance of family-owned businesses (FOBs) in India. The study concludes that family ownership plays a pivotal role in shaping financial performance. While family firms exhibit distinct advantages in financial performance metrics, challenges arise in maintaining and enhancing their intellectual capital, which is crucial for sustaining competitiveness in a rapidly evolving economic landscape. This dual focus highlights the importance of strategic governance practices that balance family interests and professional management and help to mitigate risks associated with nepotism and entrenchment. Family firms must embrace tradition with transformation, leveraging stewardship, independent oversight, and innovation to sustain competitiveness. Such integration will help them evolve into globally resilient, knowledge-driven enterprises contributing to financial prosperity and sustainable economic growth.

References

Aguinis, H., Edwards, J.R. and Bradley, K.J. (2017) 'Improving our understanding of moderation and mediation in strategic management research', *Organizational Research Methods*, 20(4), pp. 665–685.

Anderson, R.C., Mansi, S.A. and Reeb, D.M. (2003) 'Founding family ownership and the agency cost of debt', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 68(2), pp. 263–285.

Bang, N.P., Ray, S., Ramachandran, K. and Vishwanathan, A., 2018. Family businesses: promoters' skin in the game 2001-2017. *White Paper, June, available at: www.isb.edu/sites/default/files/Family-Businesses-Promoters-Skin-in-the-Game-2001-2017_0_1.pdf (accessed 24 March 2020).*

Bauweraerts, J., Pongelli, C., Sciascia, S., Mazzola, P. and Minichilli, A. (2023) 'Transforming entrepreneurial orientation into performance in family SMEs: Are nonfamily CEOs better than family CEOs?', *Journal of Small Business Management*, 61(4), pp. 1672–1703.

Bazhair, A.H. and Sulimany, H.G.H. (2023) 'Does family ownership moderate the relationship between board diversity and the financial performance of Saudi-listed firms?', *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 11(4), p. 118.

Bhatt, R.R. and Bhattacharya, S. (2017) 'Family firms, board structure and firm performance: Evidence from top Indian firms', *International Journal of Law and Management*, 59(5), pp. 699–717.

Block, J., Jarchow, S., Kammerlander, N., Hosseini, F. and Achleitner, A.K. (2020) 'Performance of foundation-owned firms in Germany: The role of foundation purpose, stock market listing, and family involvement', *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 11(4), 100356.

Bodolica, V., Dupuis, D. and Spraggon, M. (2020) 'At the intersection of corporate governance and performance in family business settings: Extant knowledge and future research', *Business Ethics: A European Review*, 29(1), pp. 143–166.

Chahal, H. and Sharma, A.K. (2022) 'Family involvement in ownership, management and firm performance: Evidence from Indian listed companies', *Indian Journal of Corporate Governance*, 15(1), pp. 26–47.

Evert, R.E., Sears, J.B., Martin, J.A. and Payne, G.T. (2018) 'Family ownership and family involvement as antecedents of strategic action: A longitudinal study of initial international entry', *Journal of Business Research*, 84, pp. 301–311.

Gill, S. and Kaur, P. (2015) 'Family involvement in business and financial performance: A panel data analysis', *Vikalpa*, 40(4), pp. 395–420.

Giovannini, R. (2010) 'Corporate governance, family ownership and performance', *Journal of Management and Governance*, 14, pp. 145–166.

Goel, S., Mazzola, P., Phan, P.H., Pieper, T.M. and Zachary, R.K. (2012) 'Strategy, ownership, governance, and socio-psychological perspectives on family businesses from around the world', *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 3(2), pp. 54–65.

Gupta, A. and Nashier, T. (2017) 'Family ownership and firm performance: Evidence from India', *Quarterly Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 55(3–4), pp. 37–68.

Ha, N.M., Do, B.N. and Ngo, T.T. (2022) 'The impact of family ownership on firm performance: A study on Vietnam', *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 10(1), 2038417.

- Jaskiewicz, P., Combs, J.G. and Rau, S.B. (2015) 'Entrepreneurial legacy: Toward a theory of how some family firms nurture transgenerational entrepreneurship', *Journal of Business Venturing*, 30(1), pp. 29–49.
- Keasey, K., Martinez, B. and Pindado, J. (2015) 'Young family firms: Financing decisions and the willingness to dilute control', *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 34, pp. 47–63.
- Koji, K., Adhikary, B.K. and Tram, L. (2020) 'Corporate governance and firm performance: A comparative analysis between listed family and non-family firms in Japan', *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 13(9), p. 215.
- Kosmidou, V. (2020). A meta-analytic examination of the relationship between family firm generational involvement and performance. *Management Research Review*, 43(8), 971-987.
- Lambrecht, J. and Lievens, J. (2008) 'Pruning the family tree: An unexplored path to family business continuity and family harmony', *Family Business Review*, 21(4), pp. 295–313.
- Le Breton-Miller, I. and Miller, D. (2009) 'Agency vs. stewardship in public family firms: A social embeddedness reconciliation', *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 33(6), pp. 1169–1191.
- Miller, D., Le Breton-Miller, I., Amore, M.D., Minichilli, A. and Corbetta, G. (2017) 'Institutional logics, family firm governance and performance', *Journal of Business Venturing*, 32(6), pp. 674–693.
- Minh Ha, N., Do, B. N., & Ngo, T. T. (2022). The impact of family ownership on firm performance: A study on Vietnam. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 10(1), 2038417.
- Morck, R. and Yeung, B. (2003) 'Agency problems in large family business groups', *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 27(4), pp. 367–382.
- Moreno-Gené, J. and Gallizo, J.L. (2021) 'Intergenerational differences in family business management and their influence on business profitability', *Sustainability*, 13(12), p. 6979.
- Muttakin, M.B., Khan, A. and Subramaniam, N. (2014) 'Family firms, family generation and performance: Evidence from an emerging economy', *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 4(2), pp. 197–219.
- Neubaum, D.O., Thomas, C.H., Dibrell, C. and Craig, J.B. (2017) 'Stewardship climate scale: An assessment of reliability and validity', *Family Business Review*, 30(1), pp. 37–60.
- Pandey, R., Taylor, D. and Joshi, M. (2011) 'Family presence and financial performance in large listed companies in India', *Asia-Pacific Journal of Management Research and Innovation*, 7(1), pp. 1–15.

Poutziouris, P., Savva, C.S. and Hadjielias, E. (2015) 'Family involvement and firm performance: Evidence from UK listed firms', *Journal of Family Business Strategy*, 6(1), pp. 14–32.

Reddy, K. and Wellalage, N.H. (2023) 'Effects of family ownership and family management on the performance of entrepreneurial firms', *Research in International Business and Finance*, 65, 101977.

Rouyer, E. (2016). Family ownership and busy boards: impact on performance. *Management Decision*, 54(4), 832-853.

Sacristán-Navarro, M., Gómez-Ansón, S. and Cabeza-García, L. (2011) 'Family ownership and control, the presence of other large shareholders, and firm performance', *Family Business Review*, 24(1), pp. 71–93.

Sani, A. (2020) 'Managerial ownership and financial performance of Nigerian listed firms: The moderating role of board independence', *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 10(3), pp. 64–73.

Sarbah, A., Quaye, I. and Affum-Osei, E. (2015) 'Corporate governance in family businesses: The role of non-executive and independent directors', *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 4(1), pp. 14–35.

Shyu, J., & Shen, Y. H. (2011). How Does Family Management Affect Firm Performance: Evidence from Taiwanese Firms. *Electronic Journal of Family Business Studies (EJFBS)*.

Srivastava, A. and Bhatia, S. (2022) 'Influence of family ownership and governance on performance: Evidence from India', *Global Business Review*, 23(5), pp. 1135–1153.

Sunon, K.H., Islam, M.T. and Kabir, M.A. (2022) 'Impact of family succession on financial performance: Empirical evidence from Bangladesh', *Journal of Family Business Management*, 12(2), pp. 337–354.

Thorning-Lund, S. (2012) *Keeping it in the family? How independent directors add value to family businesses*. London: Odgers Berndtson.

Villalonga, B. and Amit, R. (2006) 'How do family ownership, control and management affect firm value?', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 80(2), pp. 385–417.

Vu, V.T.T., Phan, N.T. and Dang, H.N. (2020) 'Impacts of ownership structure on systemic risk of listed companies in Vietnam', *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(2), pp. 107–117.

Yu, J. and Cai, X. (2017) 'The influence of intergenerational succession of family business on its performance: Enterprise innovation as a mediating variable', *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 7(6), pp. 798–815.

Wu, Q., Wang, Y., Chu, H., & Chen, J. (2025). Innovation in Family Firms: An Intergenerational Tale of Symbol and Substance. *Management and Organization Review*, 1-32.

Zhang, W., Wu, B., Chen, L., Zhu, J.A. and Chen, S., 2025. How do family firms balance economic and non-economic goals: from symbiosis to competition. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, p.1538103.

Web sources

Economic Times (2013) *With 73% of the top 500 firms on BSE being family-run, Constitution keeps business families together*. Available at: <https://m.economictimes.com/news/company/corporate-trends/with-73-of-the-top-500-firms-on-bse-being-family-run-constitution-keeps-business-families-together/articleshow/25191458.cms> (Accessed: Day Month Year).

EY (2021) *How the world's largest family businesses are proving their resilience*. Available at: https://www.ey.com/en_it/insights/family-enterprise/how-the-worlds-largest-family-businesses-are-proving-their-resilience (Accessed: Day Month Year).

AI Use Declaration

The authors confirm that Chat GPT and Grammarly were used solely for language editing, grammar checking and improving the clarity and coherence of the manuscript. AI tools are not used to generate ideas, perform data analysis, or interpret data.

Ethical Declaration

This study is based solely on secondary data from publicly available sources and does not involve human participants or animals. Ethical approval was therefore not required. The authors confirm adherence to accepted standards of research integrity.

Funding

No funding is received to conduct this study

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest in this research.